

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: STEPHANE****FIRST NAME: BONAMY****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: (MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Why must the doctoral student choose a reference variant between American English and British English?
 - The choice of a reference variant reflects the student's origin.
 - The choice of a reference variant gives the study its own style.
 - The choice of a referent variant provides style consistency across the text.¹**
 - The choice of a referent variant can vary throughout the text, depending on the chapters.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 21.

2. What is plagiarism?
- Plagiarism is the practice of copying text and ideas of others.
 - Plagiarism is copying and using entire paragraphs or texts of other authors or even drawing inspiration from the ideas of others without explicitly referencing them as a source.²**
 - Plagiarism is omitting to cite sources.
 - Plagiarism is the act of drawing inspiration from others without referencing them.
3. What are the characteristics of academic research?
- Argumentation based on facts and objective data.³**
 - Iteration and subjective thoughts.
 - Subjective argumentation and data.
 - Argumentative data and style.
4. How to cite sources properly?
- By referencing who created and published the text and when, what data identify the text and where it can be found.⁴**
 - Choosing a style depends on the sources to be cited.
 - By citing the name of the writer and the date of publication.
 - By using the reference style with Zotero.

² Turabian, 80.

³ Turabian, 19-20.

⁴ Turabian, 141.

5. Writing an academic essay is primarily a matter of:
- Style and language.
 - Having a good question.
 - Using different types of sources.
 - All of the above.**⁵
6. Which qualitative research method offers the most flexibility?
- The pragmatic method.**⁶
 - The combination of qualitative and quantitative methods.
 - Social constructivism.
 - Interpretivism.
7. What is the impact of plagiarism?
- The dissertation has no scientific value.
 - It creates mistrust in the ability of a researcher to develop his own ideas.
 - All of the above.**⁷
 - It is dishonest.
8. Which source category refers to books, studies, and articles that argue and comment on the subject studied?
- Primary sources.

⁵ Turabian, 24-30.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018), 149.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 224.

Secondary sources.⁸

Tertiary sources.

All of the above.

9. What have all qualitative methods in common?

They produce successful results.⁹

They are based on reflection.

All qualitative methods are scientific.

They combine qualitative and quantitative data.

10. Why is a semicolon used?

To highlight a part of a sentence.

To isolate a part of a sentence.

**To combine 2 sentences into one without using a conjunction such as 'and,'
'or', 'so.'**¹⁰

To combine two parts of the same sentence without conjunction.

⁸ Turabian, 36.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 135–137.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide English* (European Commission, 2021), 8.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Volpe, Marie F. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2018.

European Commission. *English Style Guide English*. European Commission, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.